

Study of the Azo Hydrazone Tautomerism in the 4-(9-Anthrylazo) Phenol

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Abstract : The spectroscopic study on 4-(9-anthrylazo) phenol has revealed that the azo dye under study exists in two tautomeric forms which are azo phenol and hydrazo keto forms in ratio of almost (1:1). The azo hydrazone tautomerism was confirmed by the use of IR spectroscopy and HNMR in which the characteristic absorption bands and chemical shifts for both tautomers were assigned.

Keywords : spectroscopic, tautomeric forms, azo hydrazone tautomerism, IR spectroscopy, HNMR

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